

Pharmacological applications of azomethine derivatives in the therapy of different diseases

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Abstract

Compounds with an azomethine structure belong to different chemical classes—they are hydrazones, phenylhydrazones, semicarbazones, thiosemicarbazones, and oximes. Interest in these compounds has been particularly high recently due to the fact that they exhibit a number of biological activities. The presence of an azomethine group has been found to be responsible for the anticancer, antibacterial, antiviral, anti-COVID-19, antifungal, antimalarial, anthelmintic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-Alzheimer, antidiabetic, antiarthritic, antidepressant, and antiepileptic pharmacological activities. The fragment of the azomethine group is contained in the chemical structure of a large number of drugs with applications in the treatment of various pathologies. Drugs—azomethine derivatives with the following pharmacological effects—are used in therapy: antitumor: mitoguazone, triapine, zorubicin; anti-infective: nitrofurazone, nitrofurantoin, nifurzide, nifuroxazide, nifuratel; antiviral: metisazone; antiarrhythmic: azimilide; acetylcholinesterase reactivators: pralidoxime, obidoxime, rimeboxime, methoxime; muscle relaxants: dantrolene, azumolene; antiplatelet: carbazochrome; antimigraine: iprazochrome; antidepressants: fluvoxamine; antimicrobial oxime-based cephalosporins—2nd generation: cefuroxime, cefuzonam, ceferam; 3rd generation: cefdinir, cefdaloxime, cefixime, ceftizoxime, cefetamet, cefpodoxime, cefotaxime, cefditoren, cefodizime, ceftiofur, ceferam, cefmenoxime, ceftriaxone, ceftiole, ceftazidime; 4th generation: cefepime, cefpirome, ceftazopiramide; 5th generation: ceftolozole, ceftaroline, cefiderocol.

This article reviews in detail compounds containing Schiff bases and their derivatives, including drugs with an azomethine structure, as well as their biological properties and applications.

Keywords

azomethine drugs, pharmacological effects, diseases

Introduction

I. Schiff bases

Schiff bases are compounds with an azomethine structure, which are formed as a result of the nucleophilic addition reaction of aldehydes and ketones to primary amines and which contain an azomethine group ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$) in their structure (R_1 , R_2 , and R_3 are alkyl or aryl substituents) (Fig. 1; Subasi 2022).

For the first time, azomethine derivatives were obtained by the German scientist Hugo Schiff in 1864 by condensation of a carbonyl group (aldehyde, ketone) with a primary aliphatic or aromatic amine. In the first step of the Schiff base synthesis, a carbinolamine intermediate is formed from the condensation of the carbonyl group with the primary amine, and in the second step, a Schiff base is obtained from the dehydration of the intermediate (Subasi 2022).

Figure 1. Structure of Schiff bases.

The types of amines that are condensed with carbonyl compounds are derivatives of hydroxylamine, hydrazine, phenylhydrazine, semicarbazide, thiosemicarbazide, and hydroxylamine. The names of the respective condensation products, depending on the type of amine, can be classified as hydrazones, phenylhydrazones, semicarbazones, thiosemicarbazones, and oximes (Raczuk et al. 2022).

The electron pairs on the nitrogen atom in the azomethine group determine basic properties. In Schiff compounds derived from aldehydes containing an ortho-hydroxy group, there are two tautomeric structures: phenol-imine and ketone-amine, which are identified by nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), UV-VIS spectrophotometry, and X-ray crystallography. In studies with Schiff bases derived from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and some aromatic and aliphatic amines (ammonia, methylamine, and phenylamine), it has been observed that the keto form is dominant in polar solvents, while the enol form is predominant in nonpolar solvents (Subasi 2022).

The azomethine bond ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$) is a weak chromophore that absorbs in the ultraviolet region. Conjugation with phenyl groups causes a bathochromic shift of the absorption maximum of the $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$ chromophore to the visible region. In the presence of deactivating substituents in the aromatic ring, such as a halogen atom, the wavelength of the absorption maximum decreases due to the hypsochromic effect of the substituents. The infrared bands of the $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$ bond are observed in the interval $1610\text{ cm}^{-1} - 1635\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Subasi 2022).

Over the past few decades, there has been great interest in Schiff derivatives (Al Zoubi et al. 2018; Aljamali et al. 2021). The presence of an azomethine group (Aljamali et al. 2021) has been found to be responsible for the following main important pharmacological activities of Schiff bases (Chaubey and Pandeya 2012): antitumor (Howsaui et al. 2021) and antibacterial (Chen et al. 2019; Gacitúa et al. 2022).

1. Antitumor activity of Schiff derivatives

It has been described that the anticancer effect is exerted by Schiff bases of:

1. Isatin (Liang et al. 2014) and pyrazole (Hassan et al. 2023);
2. Benzimidazole and its complexes (Magd-El-Din et al. 2018);
3. Bases containing nitro groups (Aljamali et al. 2021);
4. Co(II), Ni(II), and Cu(II) complexes of Schiff bases of 4-amino-5-(pyridin-4-yl)-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (Tyagi et al. 2015).

Bases of 5-chloroisatin (Pervez et al. 2016), sulfamoylisatin (Meenakshi et al. 2015), and 5-morpholinofonylisatin (Ammar et al. 2018) have been studied for antitumor properties. It has been found that bis-bases of 5-chloroisatin and their Cu(II) complexes are effective against the H157 lung carcinoma cell line (Pervez et al. 2016). Phenylenediamine, 5-morpholinofonylisatin, and bis(morpholinofonyl)-2-indolinone Schiff analogues with antiproliferative activity towards the HCT116 cell line have been obtained (Iacopetta et al. 2011; Ammar et al. 2018).

Schiff derivatives and their metal complexes (Tadele and Tsega 2019) exhibit antitumor activity, such as Pt(II) complexes based on Schiff bases with effects in breast cancer (Moghadam et al. 2023).

2. Antimicrobial activity of Schiff bases

It has been shown that Schiff compounds containing nitro groups possess antimicrobial effects (Aljamali et al. 2021). Schiff derivatives of 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde exert antibacterial activity against strains of *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Micrococcus luteus*. Schiff compounds of salicylaldehyde have antibacterial properties towards *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Schiff agents synthesized from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and α -amino acids (L-tyrosine, L-arginine, and L-lysine) and their manganese complexes are potential antibacterial agents against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria (Mukhtar et al. 2021). Bis-Schiff bases, derivatives of 5-substituted isatins with diamines such as 4,4'-diaminophenyl and 3,3-dimethoxybenzidine, give bis-N-[(1,3-dihydro)-2H-indol-2-one]4,4'-diamino-1,1-biphenyl derivatives, which are effective against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and fungi (*Aspergillus flavus* and *Candida albicans*) (Kandile et al. 2017). Bis-Schiff bases, derivatives of 3-(4-aminophenylimino)-5-fluoro-2H-indolin-2-one (Nirma et al. 2010) and of 5-nitroisatin (Prakash and Raja 2013), exhibit activity against the bacterial strains *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Micrococcus luteus*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and against *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Aspergillus niger* (Nirma et al. 2010; Prakash and Raja 2013).

Metal complexes of Schiff bases have been studied for antibacterial properties (Waddai et al. 2018; Jorge et al. 2024). Schiff analogues of isatin and 2,3-diaminobutane and their metal complexes are potentially effective against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Candida albicans* (Katherashala and Bollam 2014). Compared to chloramphenicol, the palladium complex of a bis-Schiff base synthesized by condensation of isatin with 1,3-diaminopropane has been confirmed to possess stronger activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* (Shukla et al. 2015). Bis-Schiff bases of isatin with ciprofloxacin are active against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Prakash and Raja 2013). Bis-Schiff derivatives of 5-methoxyisatin with thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde have been found to

be more active than amoxicillin against *Staphylococcus aureus* (Al-Mudhafar and Kamoon 2020).

The mechanisms of action of Schiff bases on microorganisms depend on the metabolic processes and the structure of the cell wall. One hypothesis is that the cell wall of microorganisms is disrupted as a result of hydrogen bonds forming between the imine groups of Schiff derivatives and the active centers of microbial cells. Another mechanism involves denaturation of one or more cellular proteins, which disrupts normal cellular functions. The effect may also be based on the ability of the imine groups of Schiff analogues to form complexes with metals Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Ca^{2+} , which are necessary for bacterial metabolic processes and growth. The stronger activity of bis-Schiff bases of isatin is due to the presence of two imine groups ($-C=N-$), which bind more effectively to the cell wall of bacteria (Raju et al. 2022). Isatin Schiff base derivatives exert activity against fungal strains *Candida albicans*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Epidermophyton floccosum*, *Microsporium audouinii*, and *Microsporium gypseum* (Aziz et al. 2020).

Antibacterial properties exhibit bis-Schiff bases of:

1. 4-chloro-2-aminophenol and salicylaldehyde derivatives (Cinarli et al. 2012);
2. 4-methyl-2-aminophenol and aldehydes (Gürbüz et al. 2012);
3. 3,3'-diaminodipropylamine and benzaldehyde (Matar et al. 2015);
4. 5-aminopyrazole (Hassan et al. 2019);
5. Co(II), Ni(II), and Cu(II) complexes (El-Gammal et al. 2021; Sumalatha et al. 2021);
6. Co(II), Cu(II), Cd(II), and Mn(II) complexes of Schiff bases of amino acids (Pervaiz et al. 2019);
7. Isatin and 2,3-diaminobutane and their metal complexes (Katherashala and Bollam 2014).

It has been investigated that different derivatives possess antibacterial potential, such as Schiff bases of:

1. 5-nitroisatin; isatin and ciprofloxacin (Prakash and Raja 2013); 5-substituted isatins with diamines (Kandile et al. 2017);
2. 3-(4-amino)phenylimino)-5-fluoroindolin-2-one (Nirma et al. 2010);
3. Isatin with 1,3-diaminopropane and their palladium complexes (Shukla et al. 2015).

Antituberculosis activity has been demonstrated for Schiff bases of 1-alkylisatin, hydrazide of isonicotinic acid (Aboul-Fadl et al. 2003), and of isatin (1H-indole-2,3-dione) (Rangaraju et al. 2013). It has been observed that the antituberculosis effect is exerted by bis-Schiff bases of isatin with p-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and their coordination complexes with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), and Mn(II) (Sangamesh et al. 2011).

Other pharmacological activities of Schiff bases include antiviral (Chen et al. 2019; Kaushik et al. 2023),

anti-COVID-19 (Alshammari et al. 2021), antifungal (Magalhães et al. 2020), antimalarial (Aggarwal et al. 2018), anthelmintic (Mathew et al. 2010), anti-inflammatory (Sandhu et al. 2023), antioxidant (Aljamali et al. 2021), anti-Alzheimer, antiarthritic (Alkahtani et al. 2023), antidepressant (Mesripour et al. 2023), antiepileptic (Chaubey and Pandeya 2012), and antidiabetic (Abbasi et al. 2021; Daoud et al. 2022).

Bis-Schiff bases of isatin-thiazole exhibit anti-HIV properties (Meleddu et al. 2017). It has been evaluated that Schiff bases of N-substituted 2-quinolonyl-acetohydrazides possess antiviral potential (Alshammari et al. 2021).

Cinnamyl-Schiff bases are known as antifungal agents (Magalhães et al. 2020).

It has been demonstrated that Schiff bases of pyrazole possess antimalarial activity (Aggarwal et al. 2018).

Schiff bases of 1,3,4-thiadiazole derivatives exert an anthelmintic effect (Mathew et al. 2010).

It has been reported that Schiff bases of pyrazole (Alkahtani et al. 2023), thymol, and carvacrol (Kumar and Rawat 2013) exhibit antioxidant properties.

Schiff bases of pyrazole (Alkahtani et al. 2023) and coumarin (Hasan et al. 2023) can play a beneficial role against Alzheimer's disease.

It has been described that Schiff bases of isatin with 2-aminopyridine possess antiepileptic potential (Chaubey and Pandeya 2012). Antiepileptic activity has been observed for bis-Schiff bases of lamotrigine with isatin and 5-chloroisatin (Kulkarni et al. 2017).

Bis-Schiff derivatives (Daoud et al. 2022) exert an antidiabetic effect, which is due to their ability to inhibit the enzymes α -amylase and α -glucosidase (Abbasi et al. 2021).

3. Multitarget profile of activity of Schiff bases

A number of Schiff compounds have been found to exhibit a multitarget profile of activity. Esters of Schiff analogues are potential anticancer, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory agents (Noureen et al. 2013). Mono- and bis-Schiff bases of morpholine derivatives have been studied for antitumor and antimalarial activity (Jarrahpour et al. 2015). Antimicrobial and antioxidant properties of Schiff agents containing aromatic nitro groups (Vhanale et al. 2022) and Co(II), Ni(II), and Cu(II) complexes of Schiff bases have been observed (Sumalatha et al. 2021).

Schiff derivatives of 4-[(1E)-N-(2-aminoethyl)ethanimidoyl]benzene-1,3-diol have been confirmed to possess antimicrobial, antioxidant, and antitumor effects (Ejidike and Ajibade 2016). It has been reported that metal Fe(II), Co(II), Cu(II), Ni(II), and Zn(II) complexes of the Schiff base of triazole, 2-[(E)-[(3-[(Z)-(2-hydroxyphenyl)methylidene])amino]-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl]imino]methyl]phenol, obtained from the condensation reaction of 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde with 3,5-diamino-1,2,4-triazole, exhibit antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-acetylcholinesterase effects (Sumrra et al. 2018). Schiff bases of 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazole exert potential antibacterial,

antituberculosis, analgesic, and anti-inflammatory activity (Pandey et al. 2012).

It has been described that Schiff compounds derived from 4-aminoantipyrine analogues have analgesic, antipyretic, and antirheumatic properties (Mukhtar et al. 2021). Pyrazole Schiff derivatives have been found to be potential antioxidant, anti-Alzheimer, antidiabetic, and antiarthritic agents (Alkahtani et al. 2023).

Schiff bases synthesized from 2-naphthaldehyde-substituted aromatic amines have been studied for antioxidant and anti-Alzheimer effects (Oladipo et al. 2023). The antiarthritic (Daoud et al. 2022) and anti-inflammatory activities are related to the ability of these agents to suppress the activity of proteinase enzymes, which is an indicator of inflammatory processes (Pandey et al. 2012).

It has been investigated that Schiff analogues of isatin (2,3-dioxindole) (Aziz et al. 2020) with aryl aldehydes, heteroaryl aldehydes, and dialdehydes are characterized by multitarget activity (Hassan et al. 2023), such as antibacterial, antiviral, and fungicidal effects (Jarrahpour et al. 2007). Antimicrobial, analgesic, and anti-inflammatory properties have been established for Schiff derivatives of 5-substituted isatin (Panneerselvam et al. 2010). Bis-Schiff bases of isatin exhibit antibacterial, antiviral, and antioxidant effects (Al-Mudhafar et al. 2022).

Antimicrobial, antifungal, and anti-inflammatory activity has been demonstrated for bis-Schiff derivatives of 5-fluorosubstituted isatin (Prakash and Raja 2013). It has been confirmed that bis-Schiff bases of 5-sulfamoyl isatin possess anti-inflammatory properties and are active against *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Aspergillus flavus*, and *Penicillium notatum* (Lingala et al. 2013).

II. Hydrazones

Compounds containing an azomethine moiety include hydrazones (Kulkarni et al. 2017), semicarbazones (Kulkarni et al. 2017), thiosemicarbazones (Güzel et al. 2008), and oximes (Dhuguru et al. 2022).

Hydrazones represent an important class of biologically active drug molecules containing an azomethine $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{NH}-$ group and are formed by the reaction of hydrazine or hydrazide with aldehydes and ketones. The azomethine structure determines a wide range of pharmacological properties of N-acylhydrazones (Thota et al. 2018; Dhuguru et al. 2022), which exhibit antitumor (Li et al. 2018; Aneja et al. 2019; Demurtas et al. 2019; Govindaiah et al. 2019; Banumathi et al. 2022; Shah et al. 2022; Vilková 2022; Kassab et al. 2023), antimicrobial (Guilherme 2019; Rezki et al. 2019; Yao et al. 2021), antituberculosis (Bonnert et al. 2018; Mandewale et al. 2019; Rohane et al. 2020), antiviral—including against Epstein-Barr virus (Reznichenko et al. 2019) and HIV (Yoneda et al. 2014)—fungicidal (Mali et al. 2021), antimalarial (dos Santos Filho et al. 2016), anti-Leishmanial (Jacomini et al. 2016; Visbal et al. 2023), anthelmintic,

antiprotozoal, antischistosome (Socea et al. 2022), and trypanocidal (Serafim et al. 2014) effects.

Antitumor activity has been demonstrated for hydrazones of acridine (Vilková 2022), coumarin (Govindaiah et al. 2019), indole (Demurtas et al. 2019), isoniazid (Shah et al. 2022), α -carboline (Li et al. 2018), and azo-hydrazones (Banumathi et al. 2022). Isatin-triazole hydrazones have been developed as potential inhibitors of microtubule kinase and are promising agents for the treatment of cell proliferation and metastasis (Aneja et al. 2019). It has been reported that azo-hydrazone analogues exert activity against solid tumors by stimulating death signaling pathways (Banumathi et al. 2022). Some indole hydrazones can be used as multifunctional agents due to their antiproliferative and antioxidant effects (Demurtas et al. 2019).

Coumarin-hydrazone derivatives have been designed as compounds targeting tubulin and reducing cancer cell growth (Govindaiah et al. 2019). α -Carboline/acylhydrazone hybrids have been discovered as antitumor agents capable of overcoming cancer drug resistance (Li et al. 2018). Hydrazone derivatives of isonicotinic hydrazide exhibit cytotoxic and antibacterial potential (Shah et al. 2022). Acridine-based N-acylhydrazone analogues have been investigated as promising anticancer agents (Vilková et al. 2022).

By inducing apoptosis, the derivative 5-bromo-1-methyl-N'-[(E)-(1-methyl-1H-indol-3-yl)methylidene]-1H-indol-3-carbohydrazide possesses anticancer activity in breast and colon tumors. The compound 1-(4-methoxybenzyl)-N'-(7-methyl-2-oxindolin-3-ylidene)-1H-1,2,3-triazole-4-carbohydrazide has shown antiproliferative effects (Aneja et al. 2019). The derivatives N'-(1-(4,7-dihydroxy-2-oxo-2H-chromen-3-yl)ethylidene)benzohydrazide and N'-(1-(4-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-chromen-3-yl)ethylidene)benzohydrazide exert antiproliferative activity comparable to doxorubicin.

Acylhydrazones exhibit antimicrobial effects against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Clostridium difficile*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Streptococcus mutans*, and possess antiparasitic activity toward *Entamoeba histolytica*, *Leishmania amazonensis*, and *Trypanosoma cruzi* (Socea et al. 2022).

Antibacterial effects are exhibited by hydrazones of isoniazid (Shah et al. 2022), pyridine (Rezki et al. 2019), and aminoguanine (Yao et al. 2021). Acylhydrazones derived from carbohydrates also demonstrate antimicrobial activity (Guilherme 2019). Pyridinium hydrazone-phenoxy conjugates have been evaluated for targeting resistant microbial strains due to their antibacterial potential (Rezki et al. 2019). Aminoguanidine derivatives containing an acylhydrazone moiety exert antimicrobial effects (Yao et al. 2021).

Hydrazones of quinoline (Mandewale et al. 2019) and eugenol (Rohane et al. 2020) are active against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (Bonnert et al. 2018). Zinc complexes of hydrazone derivatives of 3,4-dihydroquinolin-2-one have

been studied for antitubercular properties (Mandewale et al. 2019). Hydrazones of eugenol have been developed as in vitro antimycobacterial agents (Rohane et al. 2020).

Bis(acylhydrazones) are modulators of Epstein–Barr virus immune evasion (Reznichenko et al. 2019). Oxoquinoline-acylhydrazone derivatives have been reported as inhibitors of HSV-1 DNA polymerase and may be used against HIV-1 (Yoneda et al. 2014).

Anti-leishmanial properties have been established for naphthylacylhydrazones (Visbal et al. 2023) and pyrazolohydrazones (Jacomini et al. 2016). Some antimalarial compounds have been obtained from conjugation of N-acylhydrazone and 1,2,4-oxadiazoles (dos Santos Filho et al. 2016). Zinc(II)-sterol hydrazone complexes exhibit antiparasitic action against *Leishmania* (Visbal et al. 2023).

Pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyridazinone-N-acylhydrazone-(bi) thiophene hybrids have been reported to possess activity against *Leishmania amazonensis* (Jacomini et al. 2016). Hybrid derivatives of N-acylhydrazone and furan groups exert selective anti-*Trypanosoma cruzi* effects (Serafim et al. 2014).

Hydrazone derivatives are potential antidiabetic (Tariq et al. 2019), anti-inflammatory (Cordeiro et al. 2016, 2020), analgesic (Marchev et al. 2019), antioxidant (Demurtas et al. 2019; El-Mekabaty et al. 2021), anti-acetylcholinesterase (Bozbey et al. 2020), and antiglaucoma (Bozbey et al. 2020) agents. Hydrazone derivatives have also been studied for anticonvulsant (Marchev et al. 2019; Nesterkina et al. 2020), antihypertensive, antiplatelet, cardiotoxic (de Oliveira et al. 2020), and immunomodulatory effects (Meira et al. 2018).

Xanthenone-based hydrazones are α -glucosidase inhibitors and exhibit antidiabetic function (Tariq et al. 2019). The antidiabetic effect of flurbiprofen hydrazone Schiff bases has been studied (Alam et al. 2022).

Hydrazones possess anti-inflammatory activity. Tetrahydronaphthyl-N-acylhydrazones exhibit in vivo anti-TNF- α effects and can reduce inflammatory processes (Cordeiro et al. 2016). Anti-inflammatory potential has also been demonstrated for 2-aminopyridinyl-N-acylhydrazones (Cordeiro et al. 2020).

Analgesic activity has been confirmed for some hydrazones, including aryhydrazone-based hybrids (Marchev et al. 2019). Indole hydrazones with antioxidant effects have been designed (Demurtas et al. 2019). Benzenesulfonamide hydrazones have been found to inhibit carbonic anhydrase (Sharma et al. 2019). Verbenone hydrazones show anticonvulsant properties (Nesterkina et al. 2020).

Guanylhya zones are widely studied molecules of great scientific interest due to their broad biological potential, including antitumor (Franca et al. 2016), antibacterial (Gad et al. 2000), antimalarial, antihypertensive, antidiabetic, and trypanocidal activities (Azevedo de Brito et al. 2017).

Guanylhya zones exhibit biological activity against lung, breast, and glioma tumors. The 3-nitrophenyl and 4-nitrophenyl moieties of guanylhya zones are import-

ant pharmacophoric groups that enhance affinity for specific tumor receptors. The guanylhya zone derivatives 2-[(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)methylene]hydrazinecarboximidamide, 2-([1,10-biphenyl]-4-ylmethylene)hydrazinecarboximidamide, and 2-[(3,4-dichlorophenyl)methylene]hydrazinecarboximidamide possess pharmacological activity against neoplastic cell lines such as colon (HCT-8), melanoma (MDA-MB435), glioblastoma (SF-295), and promyelocytic leukemia (HL-60) (Franca et al. 2016).

A number of hydrazones have been found to exhibit a multitargeted mechanism of action against various diseases, thus making them useful drug candidates. The broad biological potential of hydrazones encourages their continued exploration for new pharmacological applications.

III. Thiosemicarbazones

Thiosemicarbazones are condensation products of thiosemicarbazide with an aldehyde or ketone (Mate sanz et al. 2021), and they exert antitumor (Shakya and Yadav 2020), antiviral (Moharana et al. 2020), fungicidal (Altıntop et al. 2016), antimalarial (Matsa et al. 2019; Anant et al. 2022), trypanocidal (Silva et al. 2019), anti-Alzheimer (Palanimuthu et al. 2017; Mavroidi et al. 2022), antioxidant (Yang et al. 2020), and antidiabetic (Shehzad et al. 2019) effects.

Thiosemicarbazones have demonstrated activity against Alzheimer's disease in vitro (Mavroidi et al. 2022). The antioxidant properties of camphene-based thiosemicarbazones have been evaluated (Yang et al. 2020). The antidiabetic potential of adamantyl-thiosemicarbazones has been explored, and it has been shown that this effect results from the inhibition of aldose reductase (Shehzad et al. 2019).

Some thiosemicarbazones exhibit multitarget activity. Naphthalene-substituted thiosemicarbazone derivatives have been shown to be potent antifungal and anticancer agents (Altıntop et al. 2016). Thiosemicarbazones and semicarbazones containing the 1,2,3-1H-triazole-isatin scaffold possess cytotoxic and trypanocidal activity (Silva et al. 2019).

Pyridoxal 4-N-(1-benzylpiperidin-4-yl)thiosemicarbazone exhibits antiproliferative effects, inhibits amyloid- β aggregation, suppresses oxidative stress, and exerts moderate anti-acetylcholinesterase activity (Palanimuthu et al. 2017). A multitargeting effect is also demonstrated by a Zn(II) thiosemicarbazone complex, which is active against SARS-CoV-2 and exhibits anti-inflammatory properties (Arslan et al. 2023). Quinazolinone thiosemicarbazones and their metal complexes possess antitumor, antimicrobial, antiepileptic, and analgesic activities (Aly et al. 2010). The compound 4-(1-adamantyl)-3-thiosemicarbazone is effective against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, as well as *Candida albicans* (Pham et al. 2020).

Thiosemicarbazone derivatives exert anticancer activity against various cell lines, including cholangiocarcinoma (HuCCA-1), liver carcinoma (HepG2),

and lung carcinoma (A549) (Shakya and Yadav 2020). Isatin-based thiosemicarbazones have been reported to exhibit antiproliferative activity against acute lymphoblastic leukemia (MOLT-3) cells (Saranya et al. 2019). Antitumor effects have also been demonstrated for thiosemicarbazone complexes with Au(I) (González-Barcia et al. 2019), bis(thiosemicarbazones) of Zn(II) (Palma et al. 2019), and Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), and Pd(II) complexes derived from 2-acetyl-5-chlorothiophene thiosemicarbazone (Şen et al. 2019).

The following thiosemicarbazones (de Siqueira et al. 2019; Heffeter et al. 2019) have shown promising antitumor properties:

1. 1-indanone (Sólamo et al. 2018) and Ga(III) (Qi et al. 2018);
2. Pyridine and quinoline (Mrozek-Wilczkiewicz et al. 2019);
3. 5-nitrothiophene (Roque-Marques et al. 2019);
4. Bromophenol (Guo et al. 2019);
5. Cu(II) complexes of chitosan (Adhikari et al. 2023);
6. Cu(II), Zn(II) (Anjum et al. 2019);
7. thiophene and cinnamaldehyde (Nyawade et al. 2021);
8. Fe(III) and Cu(II) (Kallus et al. 2019);
9. Indole (He et al. 2019).

It has been reported that *N*4-aryl-substituted thiosemicarbazones derived from 1-indanones (Sólamo et al. 2018) and gallium(III)-thiosemicarbazone complexes (Qi et al. 2018) are potential antitumor agents for breast cancer treatment.

Derivatives of 5-nitro-thiophene-thiosemicarbazone have demonstrated anticancer activity, with a mechanism of action involving the induction of apoptosis and stimulation of DNA intercalation (Roque-Marques et al. 2019). Bromophenol-thiosemicarbazone hybrids have been evaluated as potent, selective inhibitors of poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase-1, suggesting promising anticancer potential (Guo et al. 2019). The *in vitro* antitumor activity of copper and zinc bis(thiosemicarbazone) complexes has also been demonstrated (Anjum et al. 2019). Thiosemicarbazones derived from 2-acetyl-5-methylthiophene and cinnamaldehyde, along with their palladium(II) complexes, have been investigated for antiproliferative effects (Nyawade et al. 2021). In addition, biotin-conjugated anticancer thiosemicarbazones and their iron(III) and copper(II) complexes have been evaluated for their antitumor properties (Kallus et al. 2019). Thiosemicarbazone derivatives of indole have been observed to exert antiproliferative activity (He et al. 2019).

Thiosemicarbazones were among the first discovered antiviral agents and, like their parent thiosemicarbazides, display activity against various viruses, including herpes simplex virus types 1 and 2, dengue virus, hepatitis C virus, and influenza virus (Moharana et al. 2020). Thiosemicarbazones containing benzene, thiophene, or pyridine rings

have shown activity against vaccinia virus infection, with the strongest effects observed for thiosemicarbazones of:

1. Benzaldehyde and p-acetamido-, p-methoxy-, p-propoxy-, and p-ethylsulfanyl analogues;
2. *P*-aminobenzaldehyde (Moharana et al. 2020);
3. Isatin (Sevinçli et al. 2020); benzimidazole (Francesconi et al. 2020);
4. Salicylaldehyde (Rogolino et al. 2015);
5. α -amino acids (Padmanabhan et al. 2017).

P-aminobenzaldehyde-3-thiosemicarbazones were first discovered in 1950 by Hamre, Bernstein, and Donovick and were shown to exhibit antiviral activity (Moharana et al. 2020). Antiviral effects have also been reported for 5-fluoro-1H-indole-2,3-dione 3-thiosemicarbazones (Sevinçli et al. 2020). (Thio)semicarbazone-based benzimidazole derivatives have demonstrated antiviral activity against human respiratory viruses (Francesconi et al. 2020).

Salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazones have been found to inhibit influenza virus endonuclease activity (Rogolino et al. 2015). In addition, thiosemicarbazones derived from α -amino acids have been evaluated for their antiviral activity against dengue virus (Padmanabhan et al. 2017).

Currently, there is great relevance in the study of the potential activity of:

1. Schiff bases and their metal complexes with multitarget activity, such as anticancer, antibacterial, and fungicidal triazole-Schiff bases and their oxovanadium(IV) complexes (Chohan et al. 2010);
2. *N*-acylhydrazones (Kassab 2023) and metal complexes of Schiff bases with antitumor effects (Tade and Tsega 2019; Kassab 2023), such as Pt(II) complexes of Schiff bases in breast cancer (Moghadam et al. 2023);
3. Schiff bases with antimicrobial (Jorge et al. 2023), antidiabetic, antioxidant (Amine-Khodja and Boulebd 2023; Oladipo et al. 2023), and anticholinesterase (Hasan et al. 2023) properties;
4. Schiff bases of chitosan (Zarei et al. 2024);
5. Schiff bases with multitarget action.

It has been shown that multitarget action of Schiff bases derived from 2-naphthaldehyde as compounds with antidiabetic and antioxidant potential (Oladipo et al. 2023). It has been observed that 1,4-bisphenylhydrazones derivatives exert antioxidant effects and are acetylcholinesterase inhibitors (Amine-Khodja and Boulebd 2023).

IV. Application of drugs with azomethine structure

The fragment of the azomethine group is contained in the chemical structure of drugs, with possible applications in

the treatment of various pathologies. Drugs—azomethine derivatives with the following pharmacological effects are used in therapy (Socea et al. 2022):

1. Antitumor: mitoguazone (Knight et al. 1983), Triapine (Pelivan et al. 2015), zorubicin (Jelić et al. 1997);
2. Antiinfective: nitrofurazone, nitrofurantoin, nifurzide, nifuroxazide, nifuratel (Thota et al. 2018; Socea et al. 2022), furazolidone (Huttner et al. 2015);
3. Anti-*Mycobacterium*: thioacetazone (Singh et al. 2022);
4. Antiviral: metisazone (De Clercq 2010);
5. Antiarrhythmic: azimilide (VerNooy and Mangru 2005);
6. Acetylcholinesterase reactivators: pralidoxime, obidoxime, rimedoxime, and methoxime (Banerjee et al. 2014; Dhuguru et al. 2022);
7. Muscle relaxants: dantrolene (Yang et al. 2023), azumolene (Corrêa et al. 2013);
8. Antiplatelet: carbazochrome (Basile et al. 2001);
9. Antimigraine: iprazochrome (Basile et al. 2001);
10. Antidepressants: fluvoxamine (Hashimoto et al. 2022);
11. Antimicrobial oxime-based cephalosporins.

1. Anticancer drugs with azomethine structure

Antitumor drugs with azomethine structure are presented in Fig. 2.

Mitoguazone (MGBG, methylglyoxal-bis-guanylhydrazone) is a synthetic polycarbonyl derivative with antineoplastic activity against Hodgkin and non-Hodgkin lymphoma, AIDS-related lymphoma, head and neck cancer, prostate, and esophageal cancer (Knight et al. 1983). The drug induces apoptosis as a suppressor of S-adenosyl-methionine decarboxylase, which disrupts polyamine biosynthesis. The compound stimulates p53-independent programmed cell death (Davidson et al. 1998), inhibiting spermidine synthesis in lymphocytes. Mitoguazone reduces the frequency of HIV-infected cells by suppressing the integration of HIV DNA into cellular DNA in monocytes and macrophages (Jin et al. 2015). The drug is assayed by HPLC with an internal standard, amiloride (Cheng et al. 2003).

The α -N-heterocyclic thiosemicarbazone Triapine exhibits antitumor effects by inhibiting the catalytic activity of ribonucleotide reductase, the enzyme responsible for the conversion of ribonucleotides to their corresponding deoxyribonucleotides and, as a consequence, stopping DNA synthesis (Pelivan et al. 2015). Zorubicin is a benzoylhydrazone derivative of the anthracycline antineoplastic antibiotic daunorubicin. The drug interacts with topoisomerase II and inhibits DNA polymerases (Jelić et al. 1997).

2. Anti-infective drugs – hydrazone derivatives

Approved for use N-acylhydrazone drugs are nitrofurazone, nitrofurantoin, nifurzide, nifuroxazide, and nifuratel (Fig. 3) (Thota et al. 2018; Socea et al. 2022).

Furazolidone is a nitrofuran antibacterial agent and has a broad spectrum of activity, being active towards Gram-positive bacteria *Clostridium perfringens*, *Corynebacterium pyogenes*, streptococci, and staphylococci; Gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella Dublin*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, and *Shigella*; and protozoa *Giardia lamblia*, *Eimeria*, and *Histomonas meleagridis* (Machado et al. 2008). Nitrofurantoin possesses antibacterial activity against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Citrobacter*, *Escherichia coli*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Klebsiella*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus saprophyticus*, and *Streptococcus agalactiae*. Its efficacy in the treatment of urinary tract infections, combined with low bacterial resistance to this agent, makes it one of the first-line agents for the treatment of uncomplicated urinary tract infections, recommended by the Infectious Diseases Society of America and the European Society for Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (Huttner et al. 2015).

Nifuroxazide is an oral nitrofuran anti-infective drug and is active against bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella*, *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, and staphylococci (Baillly 2019; Sarvi et al. 2019). Nifuratel is a topical antiprotozoal and antifungal drug and is effective against *Chlamydia trachomatis* and *Mycoplasma*. Nifurzide is an anti-infective agent useful towards Chagas infection (Forsyth et al. 2016).

Anti-infective drugs – hydrazones are illustrated in Fig. 3.

Figure 2. Chemical structures of antitumor drugs with an azomethine structure.

Figure 3. Chemical structures of anti-infective drugs with an azomethine structure.

3. Antituberculosis, antiviral, and antiarrhythmic drugs with azomethine structure

Fig. 4 presents the chemical structures of thioacetazone, methisazone, and azimilide.

Thioacetazone (Amithiozone) exerts activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and is useful only in preventing resistance to isoniazid and rifampicin. It has been withdrawn from use due to toxicity (Singh et al. 2022). The thiosemicarbazone approved for human use is methisazone (Marboran). This compound is a thiosemicarbazone derived from the condensation of N-methylisatin with thiosemicarbazide and is effective in the prevention of smallpox. It is approved by the FDA as an antiviral drug that acts by inhibiting mRNA and protein synthesis. It has been identified as anti-SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19) (De Clercq 2010). Azimilide is a class III antiarrhythmic drug for controlling abnormal heart rhythms, affecting repolarization, and prolonging the duration of the action potential and the refractory period (VerNooy and Mangru 2005).

4. Oximes – acetylcholinesterase reactivators and antibacterial drugs

Acetylcholinesterase reactivators include pralidoxime, obidoxime, rimedoxime, and methoxime. Pralidoxime is an FDA-approved drug (Fig. 5) (Banerjee et al. 2014; Dhuguru et al. 2022).

5. Drugs – muscle relaxants with an azomethine structure

Dantrolene (Fig. 6) is a postsynaptic muscle relaxant that inhibits the release of Ca^{2+} ions from sarcoplasmic reticu-

lum stores by antagonizing ryanodine receptors. It is used for the treatment and prevention of malignant hyperthermia, a rare, life-threatening condition induced by general anesthesia (Yang et al. 2023). Azumolene (Fig. 6) is a derivative of dantrolene with lower toxicity and fewer side effects (Corrêa et al. 2013).

6. Antiplatelet, antimigraine, and antidepressant drugs with an azomethine structure

The antiplatelet drug carbazochrome (3-hydroxy-1-methyl-5,6-indolindione 5-semicarbazone) (Fig. 7) is a semicarbazone of adrenochrome. Iprazochrome (3-hydroxy-1-isopropyl-5,6-indolindione 5-semicarbazone) (Fig. 7) is a carbazochrome derivative antimigraine drug and is also used in diabetic retinopathy (Basile et al. 2001). Fluvoxamine is an antidepressant that functions as a selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor (Hashimoto et al. 2022) (Fig. 7).

7. Antimicrobial oxime-based cephalosporins: 2nd (Fig. 9), 3rd (Fig. 8), 4th, and 5th (Fig. 9) generations

Oxime-based cephalosporins are emerging as an important class of drugs with improved efficacy and a broad spectrum of antimicrobial activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative pathogens. Cefuroxime, ceftizoxime, ceftopodoxime, and ceftmenoxime are FDA-approved oxime-based antibiotics (Dhuguru et al. 2022).

Third-generation cephalosporins are used in the treatment of Gram-negative meningitis, Lyme disease, *Pseudomonas pneumonia*, and streptococcal endocarditis (Stetsiouk et al. 2023). Ceftriaxone is among the most widely used (Shirin and Islam 2020).

Figure 4. Azomethine drugs with anti-Mycobacterium, antiviral, and antiarrhythmic activity.

Figure 5. Acetylcholinesterase reactivators with an azomethine structure.

Figure 6. Chemical structures of muscle relaxants with an azomethine structure.

Figure 7. Chemical structure of carbazochrome, iprazochrome, and fluvoxamine.

Figure 8. Oxime-based cephalosporins – 3rd generation.

Figure 9. Oxime-based cephalosporins – 2nd, 4th, and 5th generations.

Third- and fourth-generation cephalosporins (Stetsiouk et al. 2023) are often combined with the beta-lactamase inhibitor sulbactam. Cefepime is a fourth-generation cephalosporin effective against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria (Yahav et al. 2007).

Ceftobiprole (Scheeren 2015), ceftaroline (Welte et al. 2019), and cefiderocol (McCreary et al. 2021) are fifth-generation cephalosporins. Ceftobiprole and ceftaroline are effective against methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). Ceftobiprole is used for the treatment of hospital-acquired pneumonia (Scheeren 2015). Cefiderocol was approved by the FDA in 2019 for urinary tract infections and in 2020 for hospital-acquired pneumonia and ventilator-associated bacterial pneumonia (McCreary et al. 2021).

Chemical structures of oxime-based cephalosporins are summarized in Fig. 8 (3rd generation) and Fig. 9 (2nd, 4th, and 5th generations).

Conclusion

Compounds containing an azomethine moiety include hydrazones, semicarbazones, thiosemicarbazones, and oximes. The azomethine group has been found to be responsible for various pharmacological effects such as anticancer, antibacterial, antiviral, anti-COVID-19, antifungal, antimalarial, anthelmintic, anti-inflammatory,

antioxidant, anti-Alzheimer, antidiabetic, antiarthritic, antidepressant, and antiepileptic activities. Approved anti-infective drugs with an N-acylhydrazone structure include nitrofurazone, nitrofurantoin, nifurzide, nifuroxazide, and nifuratel. Antitumor azomethines include mitoguazone, triapine, and zorubicin. Thioacetazone exhibits activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Acetylcholinesterase reactivators pralidoxime, obidoxime, rimedoxime, and methoxime are azomethine derivatives—oximes. Only pralidoxime is an FDA-approved drug. The semicarbazone carbazochrome is an antiplatelet drug, and its derivative iprazochrome is applied for migraine and diabetic retinopathy. Antimicrobial oxime-based cephalosporins belong to the 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th generations.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declare that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declare that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declare that no informed consent was obtained from humans, donors, or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declare that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declare that no commercially available immortalized human or animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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